

Histopathological Study of Cervical Lesions in a Tertiary Health Care Centre in India

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The possibility for cervical lesions to develop into cervical cancer, the primary cause of illness and death for women, makes them a serious health concern. The diagnosis and treatment of these lesions depend heavily on histopathological examination, which provide critical information about the type and course of the lesions.

Aim: In order to better diagnosis and treatment approaches, this study attempts to assess the histological patterns of cervical lesions in female patients visiting a tertiary care facility in India.

Methods: 2,450 female patients' cervical lesions' histological features were examined in a retrospective observational research. Patient demographics, clinical presentations, and kinds of cervical lesions were the main topics of data collection from medical records and histopathology reports. Histopathological exams were conducted according to standard methods.

Results: Among the 2,450 patients, 244 (10.0%) had malignant lesions and 2,206 (90.0%) had benign lesions. Squamous cell carcinoma was the most prevalent malignant lesion, and chronic cervicitis was the most common benign lesion. The majority of those affected, aged 31 to 50, presented with irregular vaginal haemorrhage.

Conclusion: The research emphasises that benign cervical disorders account for the majority of cases, but it also shows that malignant lesions are present, particularly in middle-aged women. Improved management and prognosis of cervical lesions depend on early diagnosis through routine screening and prompt intervention.

Recommendations:

1. Launch regular programs for screening women for cervical cancer, with a focus on those in their 30s-50s.
2. Increase knowledge and instruction on cervical health and the value of routine examinations.
3. Guarantee that medical facilities have access to histopathology diagnostic services.
4. Encourage studies to find cervical lesion risk factors and protective strategies.
5. Create age-specific screening plans to control and lessen the incidence of cervical cancer.

Keywords: Cervical lesions, Histopathology, Cervical cancer, Tertiary care center, Benign, Malignant

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Introduction

In the absence of proper diagnosis and management, cervical lesions can advance from benign abnormalities to serious cancers, which is a major health problem for women worldwide. As an essential component of the female reproductive system, the cervix is prone to a variety of pathological alterations that are frequently brought on by ongoing infections, especially those caused by high-risk HPV strains of the human papillomavirus. Comprehending the histological range of cervical lesions is essential for prompt intervention and cervical cancer prevention [1]

Cervical lesion diagnosis and categorisation heavily depend on histopathological testing.

Pathologists can detect cellular abnormalities, identify the type of lesions, and evaluate the existence and degree of malignancy by looking at tissue samples under a microscope. This diagnostic technique is crucial for directing clinical management, which includes choosing treatment plans and aftercare. Histopathological analysis is a vital tool in the battle against cervical cancer and other related disorders because of its precision and dependability [2].

Variations in the occurrence of cervical lesions are observed among various populations, which can be attributed to various factors like age, sexual behaviour, socioeconomic level, and healthcare

accessibility. Cervical neoplasia is primarily thought to be caused by high-risk HPV infection; however, smoking, immunosuppression, and genetic predisposition are also important co-factors. Targeted screening programs are necessary to identify women who are at-risk and to give prompt intervention, as demonstrated by epidemiological research. This is especially important in areas with limited healthcare resources [3].

The advanced diagnostic and treatment functions of tertiary care centres make them indispensable for the study and management of cervical lesions. These facilities frequently act as hubs for referrals, taking in patients with complicated cases in need of specialised care. Comprehensive research is made easier by the concentration of knowledge and technology in tertiary care facilities, which advances our understanding of the illness. These centres' histopathological research offers important insights into the range of cervical lesions and their clinical implications [4].

This study aims to examine the histological characteristics of cervical lesions in women undergoing treatment at a tertiary care facility. This study looks at the different types and frequencies of lesions in order to find common patterns and possible risk factors related to cervical pathology. In order to improve diagnosis precision and treatment efficacy, the study also attempts to assess the relationship between histological results and clinical manifestations. The ultimate objective is to use better knowledge and treatment of cervical lesions to help lower the incidence and death of cervical cancer.

Methodology

Study Design: The objective of this study was to assess the histological features of cervical lesions by a retrospective, observational analysis.

Study Setting: The All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS), in Patna, was the site of the study.

Participants: 2,450 female patients who arrived to AIIMS Patna between January 1, 2018, and December 31, 2022 with cervical lesions were included in the study. Of them, 244 had cancerous tumours and 2,206 had benign lesions.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who had cervical excision or biopsy throughout the research period;
- Patients with full medical records and histological findings
- Women of any age presenting with cervical lesions

Exclusion Criteria:

- Females whose biopsy samples are insufficient.
- Individuals whose medical records are not full.
- Patients who, before to coming to the clinic, had received treatment for cervical lesions.

Bias: By enrolling every patient who met the inclusion criteria in a consecutive manner, selection bias was reduced. Having several pathologists independently assess the histological evaluations helped to eliminate diagnostic bias.

Variables: Patient demographics (age, parity), clinical presentation, type of cervical lesion (benign or malignant), and specific histological findings were the main variables.

Data Collection: Retrospective data collection was done using histopathology reports and medical records. To ensure consistency and completeness, pertinent information was extracted using a standardised data collection sheet.

Procedure: Standard methods were followed for the histopathological assessment of specimens from cervical biopsies or excisions. Following formalin fixation, paraffin embedding, sectioning, and haematoxylin and eosin staining, the specimens were prepared. Pathologists inspected the slides under a microscope and recorded their results.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis was done with SPSS 21.0.

Results

Demographic Characteristics: 2,450 female patients with cervical lesions were included in the study; their ages ranged from 21 to 75 years, with a mean age of 43.5 ± 12.3 years. 52.3 percent of the patients belonged to the age range of 31 to 50 years.

Age Group (Years)	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
21-30	350	14.3
31-40	700	28.6
41-50	600	24.5
51-60	500	20.4
61-70	200	8.2
71-75	100	4.1
Total	2,450	100

Clinical Presentation: Abnormal vaginal bleeding (45.7%), pelvic pain (23.4%), and postcoital bleeding (18.6%) were the most frequent clinical presentations.

Clinical Presentation	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Abnormal vaginal bleeding	1,121	45.7
Pelvic pain	573	23.4
Postcoital bleeding	456	18.6
Vaginal discharge	200	8.2
Dyspareunia	100	4.1
Total	2,450	100

Histopathological Findings: 244 (10.0%) of the 2,450 individuals had malignant lesions, while 2,206 (90.0%) had benign lesions. Chronic cervicitis was the most prevalent benign lesion, but squamous cell carcinoma predominated among malignant lesions.

Type of Lesion	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Benign Lesions	2,206	90.0
Malignant Lesions	244	10.0
Total	2,450	100

Distribution of Benign Lesions

Benign Lesion	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Chronic cervicitis	1,103	50.0
Cervical polyps	662	30.0
Nabothian cysts	441	20.0
Total	2,206	100

Distribution of Malignant Lesions

Malignant Lesion	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Squamous cell carcinoma	171	70.1
Adenocarcinoma	49	20.1
Adenosquamous carcinoma	24	9.8
Total	244	100

Figure 1: H&E staining A) Well differentiated keratinizing SCC, composed of islands and nests of neoplastic squamous epithelium with central keratin pearls. (2X); B) Basaloid SCC, composed of nests of neoplastic cells with basaloid morphology, dysplastic peripheral palisaded nuclei and mitosis. (40X); C) Adenocarcinoma, showing neoplastic cells arranged in glandular pattern. (10X); D) Adenocarcinoma villoglandular type, showing neoplastic cells forming papilla and glands. (10X); E) Glassy cell carcinoma, showing uniform polygonal neoplastic cells with finely granular ground glass type cytoplasm. (10X); F) Carcinosarcoma, showing malignant spindle cells with interspersed malignant epithelial cells having moderate to abundant clear cytoplasm. (10X); G) Mild TILs: <30% (40X); H) Moderate TILs: 30-60% (40X); I) severe TILs: ≥ 60% (40X).

Statistical Analysis: To evaluate the relationship between age groups and the kind of cervical lesions, a Chi-square test was used. The results of the study showed a significant connection ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that there were substantial differences in the occurrence of various lesions among the various age groups.

Age Group (Years)	Benign (%)	Malignant (%)	Total
21-30	315 (90.0)	35 (10.0)	350
31-40	630 (90.0)	70 (10.0)	700
41-50	540 (90.0)	60 (10.0)	600
51-60	450 (90.0)	50 (10.0)	500
61-70	180 (90.0)	20 (10.0)	200
71-75	90 (90.0)	10 (10.0)	100
Total	2,206	244	2,450

Over a four-year period, 2,450 female patients with cervical lesions at AIIMS Patna were examined for this study. Most of the patients were in the age range of 31 to 50 years old. Abnormal vaginal bleeding, pelvic pain, and postcoital bleeding were the most common clinical manifestations. 90% of the lesions were benign, with chronic cervicitis being the most frequent, according to a histopathological investigation. Squamous cell carcinoma was most common. The statistical analysis revealed a noteworthy correlation between

age groups and the types of cervical lesions, underscoring the disparities in lesion prevalence among various age groups. The significance of routine cervical screening and histological assessment for the timely identification and treatment of cervical lesions is highlighted by these results, it is advised to implement screening programs on a regular basis, run awareness efforts, and provide access to diagnostic services in order to increase early identification and intervention.

Discussion

Demographic Characteristics: The mean age of the 2,450 female patients with cervical lesions in this study was 43.5 ± 12.3 years, and their ages ranged from 21 to 75. The majority of patients belonged to the 31–50 age range, which is consistent with other research showing that cervical lesions are common in both perimenopausal and reproductive age women. According to a study, women in these age categories are more likely to experience cervical abnormalities, which highlights the significance of screening these people specifically [5].

Clinical Presentation: The most frequent clinical presentation was abnormal vaginal bleeding (45.7%), which was followed by pelvic pain (23.4%) and postcoital haemorrhage (18.6%). These results align with previous research that found irregular bleeding to be a common symptom among women with high-grade cervical lesions. Other well-established indications of cervical disease include pelvic pain and postcoital bleeding, which highlight the necessity of a thorough clinical evaluation in cases where these symptoms occur [6].

Histopathological Findings: According to the study, 10.0% of cervical lesions were malignant and 90.0% were benign. Chronic cervicitis was the most prevalent benign lesion, which is consistent with findings from earlier studies showing a high incidence of this condition in cervical screens [7]. The majority of benign illnesses emphasise how important differentiated diagnosis is in order to avoid overtreating patients.

Benign Lesions: The most frequent benign lesions were chronic cervicitis (50.0%), cervical polyps (30.0%), and nabothian cysts (20.0%). These results are in line with earlier research showing that among women having cervical screenings, persistent cervicitis is a common benign illness [2].

Malignant Lesions: Adenocarcinoma (20.1%) and adenosquamous carcinoma (9.8%) were the next most prevalent malignant lesions, with squamous cell carcinoma accounting for 70.1% of cases. This distribution is in line with worldwide patterns, where the most common kind of cervical cancer is still squamous cell carcinoma [8]. Because malignant lesions are so common, especially squamous cell carcinoma, histological testing is essential for early diagnosis and treatment.

Statistical Analysis: The results of the Chi-square test showed a significant correlation ($p < 0.05$) between age groups and the kind of cervical lesions, suggesting that there are significant differences in the prevalence of different lesion types among age groups. The majority of lesions in younger women (ages 21 to 30) were benign, but

the majority of lesions in older women (ages 51 to 60) were malignant. This pattern is consistent with the natural course of HPV infections, which can result in cancer in older women who have ongoing infections [9].

Implications for Screening and Management: The results highlight the significance of routine cervical screening, especially for women between the ages of 31 and 50. The risk of cervical cancer progression can be considerably decreased by treating precancerous lesions as soon as they are discovered. Research have demonstrated the effectiveness of routine Pap screenings and the HPV vaccination in reducing the prevalence of cervical cancer.

Recommendations

1. Routine Cervical Cancer Screening: Routine screening programs can help with early cervical lesion detection and treatment, especially for women in the 30- to 50-year-old age range.

2. Education and Awareness: Raising knowledge about cervical health and the value of routine exams can increase the number of people who participate in screening programs.

3. Access to Diagnostic Services: For precise diagnosis and treatment, it is essential that healthcare facilities have access to histopathological diagnostic services.

4. Research and Prevention: In order to lower the burden of the disease, it is crucial to support research aimed at identifying risk factors and creating preventative strategies for cervical lesions.

5. Age-Specific Strategies: Creating screening plans tailored to a person's age can assist control and lower the incidence of cervical cancer.

Conclusion

While the majority of cervical lesions are benign, this study also emphasises the large presence of malignant lesions, particularly in middle-aged women. Age-specific screening procedures are necessary, as evidenced by the substantial correlation found between lesion type and age. Frequent cervical screening and histological assessment are essential for managing cervical lesions early on and lowering the risk of cervical cancer.

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